

Preparing References README

There are dozens of input files needed for these pipelines. These include things like reference genomes, aligner indices, gene annotations, and known variants. This guide aims to be a comprehensive walkthrough of where to find those files and/or how to create them. Code snippets are included for human build GRCh38 and Ensembl version 113.

Before running any snippets, make a directory where you'd like this cache to be stored, and set the **BASEDIR** variable to point to it:

```
BASEDIR=/path/to/annotation_data_grch38_ens113
```

Reference genome

fasta

We will use the 1000 Genomes version of the human GRCh38 build. This reference includes extra decoy and HLA sequences in addition to the alternate haplotypes provided from the GRC consortium.

```
mkdir -p $BASEDIR/reference_genome
wget -O $BASEDIR/reference_genome/all_sequences.fa
https://ftp.1000genomes.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/ftp/technical/reference/GRCh38_reference_genome/GRCh38_full_analysis_set_plus_decoy_hla.fa
```

fasta index

From docker image **mgibio/samtools-cwl:1.0.0**

```
/opt/samtools/bin/samtools faidx
$BASEDIR/reference_genome/all_sequences.fa
```

Sequence dictionary

From docker image **mgibio/picard-cwl:2.18.1**

```
java -jar /opt/picard/picard.jar CreateSequenceDictionary
R=$BASEDIR/reference_genome/all_sequences.fa
O=$BASEDIR/reference_genome/all_sequences.dict
```

Ensembl Synonyms file

We will download the chromAlias file from UCSC genome browser and restrict it to lines in Ensembl

```
wget -O $BASEDIR/reference_genome/chromAlias.txt.gz
https://hgdownload.soe.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg38/database/chromAlias.txt.gz
zgrep 'ensembl' chromAlias.txt.gz > chromAlias.ensembl.txt
rm chromAlias.txt.gz
```

Ensembl/VEP annotation files

VEP cache

Select the most recent [docker image from your desired ensembl version](#). Our current release uses [ensemblorg/ensembl-vep:release_113.3](#) Inside that container, run the following (mount the appropriate volumes if needed):

```
mkdir $BASEDIR/vep_cache
/usr/bin/perl /opt/vep/src/ensembl-vep/INSTALL.pl --CACHEDIR
$BASEDIR/vep_cache --AUTO cf --SPECIES homo_sapiens --ASSEMBLY GRCh38
zip -r $BASEDIR/vep_cache.zip $BASEDIR/vep_cache
```

If for some reason the desired cache version and docker image version in use do not match, add `--CACHE_VERSION <version>`

Genes/Transcripts GTF

```
mkdir -p $BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation
cd $BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation
wget -O $BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf.gz
https://ftp.ensembl.org/pub/release-113/gtf/homo_sapiens/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf.gz
gunzip Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf.gz
```

The reference uses "chr" prefixes (chr1, chr2, chr3), while the Ensembl gtf does not (1, 2, 3), so we need to convert the gtf:

```
cd $BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/
wget
https://raw.githubusercontent.com/chrisamiller/convertEnsemblGTF/master/convertEnsemblGTF.pl
mv $BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf.orig
perl convertEnsemblGTF.pl $BASEDIR/reference_genome/all_sequences.dict
$BASEDIR/vep_cache/homo_sapiens/113_GRCh38/chr_synonyms.txt
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf.orig
>$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf && rm -f
```

```
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf.orig 2>
convertEnsemblGTF.stdout
```

Transcriptome cDNA reference

Note that we're not going to convert these coordinates from [1,2,3] to [chr1,chr2,chr3], since Kallisto doesn't include coordinates in it's output. If pseudobams from kallisto are desired, that conversion would need to be done. We will get both the coding (cdna) and non-coding (ncrna) files and combine them.

```
wget -O $BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.cdna.all.fa.gz
https://ftp.ensembl.org/pub/release-
113/fasta/homo_sapiens/cdna/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.cdna.all.fa.gz
wget -O $BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.ncrna.fa.gz
https://ftp.ensembl.org/pub/release-
113/fasta/homo_sapiens/ncrna/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.ncrna.fa.gz

cat $BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.cdna.all.fa.gz
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.ncrna.fa.gz >
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.cdna.ncrna.fa.gz
```

Aligner indices

bwa mem index

From docker image: [mgibio/alignment_helper-cwl:2.1.1](#)

```
mkdir -p $BASEDIR/aligner_indices/bwamem_0.7.15
cd $BASEDIR/aligner_indices/bwamem_0.7.15
for i in all_sequences.fa all_sequences.fa.fai all_sequences.dict
all_sequences.genome;do
    ln -s $BASEDIR/reference_genome/$i .
done
bwa-mem2 index all_sequences.fa
```

STAR-fusion index

In the [trinityctat/starfusion](#) docker container:

```
mkdir -p $BASEDIR/aligner_indices/star_fusion/temp
cd $BASEDIR/aligner_indices/star_fusion/temp
/usr/local/src/STAR-Fusion/ctat-genome-lib-builder/prep_genome_lib.pl --
CPU 10 --genome_fa $BASEDIR/reference_genome/all_sequences.fa --gtf
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf --pfam_db current
--dfam_db human --output_dir $BASEDIR/aligner_indices/star_fusion
#based on logfile, this was unsuccessful => issue might be solved by
entering a temporary directory but running the rest of the command the
```

```
same way.  
# temp directory worked. Now just need to figure out which files to zip.  
Will use our actual starfusion.zip dir as reference; copying to  
temp_real_star_fusion_dir and unzipping.
```

Known Variants

Known snps and indels

dbSNP/indels from the Mills/1000G/etc datasets for use with GATK/Mutect from the [google/cloud-sdk](#) image:

```
mkdir $BASEDIR/known_variants  
gsutil -m cp -r gs://genomics-public-  
data/resources/broad/hg38/v0/Homo_sapiens_assembly38.dbsnp138.vcf  
$BASEDIR/known_variants  
gsutil -m cp -r gs://genomics-public-  
data/resources/broad/hg38/v0/Mills_and_1000G_gold_standard.indels.hg38.vcf  
.gz $BASEDIR/known_variants  
gsutil -m cp -r gs://genomics-public-  
data/resources/broad/hg38/v0/Mills_and_1000G_gold_standard.indels.hg38.vcf  
.gz.tbi $BASEDIR/known_variants  
gsutil -m cp -r gs://genomics-public-  
data/resources/broad/hg38/v0/Homo_sapiens_assembly38.known_indels.vcf.gz  
$BASEDIR/known_variants  
gsutil -m cp -r gs://genomics-public-  
data/resources/broad/hg38/v0/Homo_sapiens_assembly38.known_indels.vcf.gz.t  
bi $BASEDIR/known_variants
```

DoCM cancer variants

Variants from the [Database of Canonical Mutations](#) used for hotspot checking in somatic pipelines

```
wget -O $BASEDIR/known_variants/docm.vcf.gz https://github.com/evelyn-  
schmidt/immuno_gcp_wdl_manuscript/raw/refs/heads/main/reference_inputs/doc  
m.vcf.gz  
wget -O $BASEDIR/known_variants/docm.vcf.gz.tbi https://github.com/evelyn-  
schmidt/immuno_gcp_wdl_manuscript/raw/refs/heads/main/reference_inputs/doc  
m.vcf.gz.tbi
```

Gnomad population frequencies

This command downloads the V3 of the genome [Gnomad Database](#) which has the allele frequencies from 70k WGS samples aligned to GRCh38. This file is ~236gb.

```
#Download gnomad V3 VCFs for each chromosome, concatenate, and filter to
AF>0.001.
mkdir $BASEDIR/known_variants/gnomad_temp
# Step 1: Download VCFs
for chr in {1..22} X Y; do
  wget
  https://ftp.ensembl.org/pub/data_files/homo_sapiens/GRCh38/variation_genot
  ype/gnomad/v3.1.2/gnomad.genomes.v3.1.2.sites.chr${chr}_trimmed_info.vcf.b
  gz
done

# Step 2: Concatenate bgzipped VCFs (headers only from first file)
bcftools concat -Oz -o gnomad.genomes.v3.1.2.concatenated.vcf.bgz \
  gnomad.genomes.v3.1.2.sites.chr{1..22}_trimmed_info.vcf.bgz \
  gnomad.genomes.v3.1.2.sites.chrX_trimmed_info.vcf.bgz \
  gnomad.genomes.v3.1.2.sites.chrY_trimmed_info.vcf.bgz

# Step 3: Index the concatenated VCF
bcftools index -t gnomad.genomes.v3.1.2.concatenated.vcf.bgz

# Step 4: Restrict to variants with AF > 0.001
bcftools view -i 'INFO/AF[0]>0.001' -Oz -o gnomad_b38_exome.vcf.gz
gnomad.genomes.v3.1.2.concatenated.vcf.bgz
bcftools index -t gnomad_b38_exome.vcf.gz

# Step 5: Copy gnomad VCF to known variants and optionally delete original
folder
cp $BASEDIR/known_variants/gnomad_temp/gnomad_b38_exome.vcf.gz*
$BASEDIR/known_variants/
```

Common SNPs for somalier concordance

```
wget -O $BASEDIR/known_variants/somalier_GRCh38.vcf.gz
https://github.com/brentp/somalier/files/3412456/sites.hg38.vcf.gz
```

Other Transcriptome files

Kallisto transcriptome index

From docker image [mgibio/rnaseq](#)

```
kallisto index -i
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.cdna.ncrna.fa.kallisto.idx
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.cdna.ncrna.fa.gz
```

Kallisto gene translation table

From docker image quay.io/biocontainers/bioconductor-biomart:2.62.0--r44hdfd78af_0

```
cd $BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/
Rscript -e 'library(biomaRt);mart <- useMart("ENSEMBL_MART_ENSEMBL",
dataset = "hsapiens_gene_ensembl");t2g <-
getBM(attributes=c("ensembl_transcript_id", "ensembl_gene_id",
"external_gene_name"), mart=mart);t2g <- t2g[order(t2g$ensembl_gene_id),
];
write.table(t2g,"ensembl113.transcriptToGene.tsv",sep="\t",row.names=F,quote=F)'
```

Refflat genes for QC

In docker container: quay.io/biocontainers/ucsc-gtftogepred:469--h664eb37_1

```
gtfToGenePred -genePredExt -geneNameAsName2 -ignoreGroupsWithoutExons
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf /dev/stdout | awk
'BEGIN { OFS="\t"} {print $12, $1, $2, $3, $4, $5, $6, $7, $8, $9, $10}'
>$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.refFlat.txt
```

Ribosomal genes for QC

```
cat $BASEDIR/reference_genome/all_sequences.dict
>$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.ribo_intervals
grep 'gene_biotype "rRNA"'
$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.gtf | awk '$3 ==
"exon" | cut -f1,4,5,7,9 | perl -lane '/transcript_id "([^"]+)"/ or die
"no transcript_id on $.";print join "\t", (@F[0,1,2,3], $1)' | sort -k1V -
k2n -k3n
>>$BASEDIR/rna_seq_annotation/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.113.ribo_intervals
```

AGFusion database

To build the AGFusion database, one can follow the instructions [here](#). However it is also necessary to generate an AGFusion docker image to run in the pipeline, therefore we suggest building a docker image and reference file automatically using the Dockerfile [here](#) as a reference point, and updating the Ensembl version as desired.

```
mkdir $BASEDIR/agfusion_1.3_database/
cd $BASEDIR/agfusion_1.3_database/
# Pull and run the docker image- ksinghal28/agfusion_ens113
```

```
# Copy the agfusion db file
cp /opt/agfusiondb/agfusion.homo_sapiens.113.db .
```

Other

Illumina adapters

```
mkdir $BASEDIR/miscellaneous
cd $BASEDIR/miscellaneous
wget -O illumina_multiplex.fa https://github.com/evelyn-
schmidt/immuno_gcp_wdl_manuscript/raw/refs/heads/main/reference_inputs/ill
umina_multiplex.fa
```

QC annotation files

```
cd $BASEDIR/aligner_indices/biscuit_0.3.8
wget http://zwdzwd.io/BISCUITqc/hg38_QC_assets.zip
unzip hg38_QC_assets.zip
```

Capture reagents

```
cd $BASEDIR/miscellaneous
wget -O IDT_xGen_Lockdown_Exome_v1.baits.interval_list
https://github.com/evelyn-
schmidt/immuno_gcp_wdl_manuscript/raw/refs/heads/main/reference_inputs/IDT
_xGen_Lockdown_Exome_v1.baits.interval_list
wget -O IDT_xGen_Lockdown_Exome_v1.targets.interval_list
https://github.com/evelyn-
schmidt/immuno_gcp_wdl_manuscript/raw/refs/heads/main/reference_inputs/IDT
_xGen_Lockdown_Exome_v1.targets.interval_list
```

Peptides FASTA file

```
cd $BASEDIR/miscellaneous
wget -O Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.pep.all.fa.gz
https://ftp.ensembl.org/pub/release-
113/fasta/homo_sapiens/pep/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.pep.all.fa.gz
```